

FACTORS INFLUENCING WORK LIFE BALANCE OF WOMEN EMPLOYEES IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY COMPANIES

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Cite This Article: Dr. K. Niranjanaa Devi & K. Jothimani, "Factors Influencing Work Life Balance of Women Employees in Information Technology Companies", *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities*, Volume 2, Issue 2, Page Number 66-69, 2017.

Abstract:

Today India is a super power in the worldwide economy in light of the skilled and taught Indian women. In a previous couple of decades, one can witness in the work showcase in India has been the passage of women data innovation (I.T) experts in the quickly developing programming administrations segment. Presently women go up against the part of working proficient in extra to their conventional work of the home creator, they are under awesome worry to adjust their work and individual life. Work Life Balance is the key issue that is irritating numerous corporate and representatives. The information relating to the investigation has been gathered from experts working in I.T. organizations in Coimbatore to distinguish the components affecting Work-life adjust and to consider the personal & hierarchical profile. The actual apparatuses like Percentage, Factor Analysis, Cluster, ANOVA and Multiple Regressions are utilized for information investigation. Examination of writing and accessible information uncovers that numerous representatives are confronting issues in altering their family life and individual existence with their authoritative workload.

Key Words: Family, Stress, Work Life Balance, Workload & Women Employee

1. Introduction:

"In India, it is underestimated that financial exercises are only the right of guys while local work, kid bearing and kid raising are the sole occupations of women's". women's have not appreciated a decent status in working environment settings whether in administrative or agent parts. In any case, with the expanding industrialization, urbanization and progressive advancements in the data innovation (IT) organizations have assumed key parts in changing the vocation examples and expert parts of women's. Work Life Balance (WLB) of women's representatives has developed as an intriguing issue as of late - since the time in this day and age, it has turned into a need that both a couple need to work to have an ordinary life as a result of the expanding financial conditions and social request. Henceforth it is exceptionally important to know how the women's adjust proficient and local life. There are different components affecting WLB, for example, push, struggle, workload, nature of work life, work family bolsters and enthusiastic savvy. Among these elements, the specialist might want to toss light on the stretch. In the underlying stages, women's needed to battle a great deal to build up their character in this focused world, both in the family and additionally in the expert life. Representatives need to appropriately manage work and family advances and characterize a limit between them in light of the fact that generally, the cover between them can bring about burnout.

1.1 Literature Review:

Tatheer Yawar Ali, Atif Hassan, Tahira Yawar Ali, and Dr. Rizwana Bashir (2013) [1] in their examination it is found that representatives confront an issue of remaining in work put for long working hours antagonistically influence their well-being and efficiency making stress. Nilgun Anafarta (2011) [2] in his examination work recognizes the relationship among WFC, FWC and employment fulfillment. This examination uncovers that WFC is by all accounts more successful on work fulfillment than FWC. Accordingly contemplating WFC by considering the social convictions, qualities, and standards is used to better comprehend WFC. Saira Ashfaq, Zahid Mahmood and Mehboob Ahmad (2013) [3] the outcomes demonstrated that representative execution is influenced by work-life struggle and work over-burden. Annie Sam and Ms. Anitha.K (2014) [4] they both uncovered that working women's can't exceed expectations in her vacation without the family bolster. Jeya Anantha Kumar and Balakrishnan Muniandi (2012) [5] attempted to investigate the general level of passionate Intelligence of representatives. The discoveries demonstrated that the levels of enthusiastic Intelligence among the addresses enhanced with age, showing background, grade, and instruction and so forth. S. Pattu Meenakshi and Dr. K. Ravichandran (2012) [6] in their investigation had examined that a considerable lot of the respondents could adjust their work and individual life despite the fact that they confront high worry at work put. The negative state of mind of companions and associates at work but was found to frustrate the work life. N. Bhuma (2012) [7] in her examination work that educators feel that the physical workplace should be adjusted and furthermore feel that legislature ought to expand their help in creating self-financing schools. Malgorzata Kluczyk (2013) [8] in his exploration establishes that the improvement or positive overflow amongst work and family areas assumes a critical part on people WLB and prosperity.

1.2 Research Gap:

The specialist found that national and worldwide analysts focused more on push, strife, workload and work family bolster factors instead of factors identifying with nature of work life, enthusiastic savvy, the effect of work life adjust on individual and on association has not be given due significance. In this manner, the analyst especially intrigued to fill the hole. In view of the recognized research hole, the particular goal of the present investigation is to distinguish and break down the commitment of stress influencing the work life adjust of women’s representatives in I.T. organizations. Also, investigated to quantify and think about the anxiety factors influencing WLB.

1.3 Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To investigate the commitment of stress influencing the work life adjust of women representatives in I.T. organizations.
- ✓ To determine and look at the anxiety factors influencing WLB of women representatives.

1.4 Hypothesis:

- ✓ H₁: There is no significant difference among contribution of stress influencing WLB of women employees.
- ✓ H₂: There is no significant difference among the stress factors affecting WLB of women employees.

1.5 Research Methodology:

- ✓ **Sample Design:** The present study was carried out in Coimbatore city by selecting I.T. professionals. A sample of 200 employees was selected for gathering primary data. To carry out the study in a more accurate and easier way, multiple random sampling methods was adopted.
- ✓ **Data Collection:** Both primary and secondary data have been used to draw appropriate conclusions. The primary data was collected by using interview and questionnaire method. The secondary data was mainly drawn from available literature pertaining to the field of knowledge.
- ✓ **Statistical Tool Used:** The collected data had been analyzed by percentage analysis, factor analysis, cluster analysis, ANOVA and multiple regression. Ten variables regarding stress and their respective influence over WLB are measured through Likert’s Five Point Scale.

2. Analysis and Discussion:

2.1 Factors of Stress Causing Work Life Balance:

The stress factors consist of ten variables in Likerts’ Five Point Scale. The reduction process of factor analysis by principle component method is applied in these ten variables and the results are presented in Table 2.1,

Table 2.1: KMO and Bartlett’s Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.780
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1365.168
	Df	45.000
	Sig.	0.000

Source: Computed Data

From the Table 2.1 it is found that KMO measure of sampling of adequacy is .780, Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity with approximately chi square value is 1365.168 are statistically significant at 5% level. Therefore it can be concluded that the sample size is adequate to reduce the variable into predominant factors. The variances exhibited by the ten variables are also significant and they formed the normal distribution. The individual variances for all the ten variables are presented in the Table 2.2.

Table 2.2: Communalities

Stress	Initial	Extraction
ST1	1.000	0.543
ST2	1.000	0.465
ST3	1.000	0.574
ST4	1.000	0.375
ST5	1.000	0.259
ST6	1.000	0.592
ST7	1.000	0.549
ST8	1.000	0.476

From the Table 2.2, it is found that the ten variables process the variance ranging from 25.9% to 59.2% (0.259 to 0.592) this implies the ten variables are significant in creating the factors through variables loading. This leads to the derivation of predominant factors from ten variables.

Table 2.3: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigen Values			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.728	37.283	37.283	2.437	24.373	24.373

2	1.101	11.010	48.293	2.392	23.921	48.293
3	0.998	9.981	58.274			
4	0.924	9.239	67.513			
5	0.775	7.753	75.266			
6	0.733	7.328	82.594			
7	0.648	6.482	89.076			
8	0.396	3.960	93.035			
9	0.352	3.522	96.558			
10	0.344	3.442	100.000			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis						

Source: Computed Data

From the Table 2.3, it is found that ten variables reduced into two predominant factors. It implies through factors process the cumulative variance 48.293%. The two factors individually process the variance 24.373% and 23.921%. These two variances are statistically significant. The variable loadings are presented in Table 2.4

Table 2.4: Rotated Component Matrix (a)

Stress	Component	
	1	2
ST3	0.753	
ST1	0.719	
ST6	0.594	
ST4	0.563	
ST2	0.522	
ST5	0.431	
ST7		0.740
ST9		0.740
ST10		0.623
ST8		0.561
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis		

Source: Computed Data

Table 2.5: The First Factor Comprises of Six Variables Statement

Factor	Statement
ST3	The demographic profile of a worker influence job stress and quality work life (0.753)
ST1	Stress management aims at balancing different work life balance situation (0.719)
ST6	Work stress leads to family imbalance (0.594)
ST4	A proper emotion management and family domain help women to solve problems of incompatibilities (0.563)
ST2	Staying in the work place for a long duration affects work life balance (0.522)
ST5	I.T. women employees are exposed to higher dosage of occupational stress (0.431)

Therefore the first factor of stress is known as “Psychological Pressure”. Psychological stress is what women employee feels when they are under pressure or having difficulty coping with a situation or stimulus. Any situation that produces an emotional response, whether it is an actual experience or one that they perceive to be real can become a source of psychological stress.

Table 2.6: The Second Factor Includes Four Variables

Factor	Statement
ST7	Relaxation options like meditation and family get together minimize the stress (0.740)
ST9	Continuous work pressure results in poor performance at work as well as at home (0.740)
ST10	Flexi time enable them to balance their work and life domain (0.623)
ST8	Higher level of stress affects job satisfaction which leads to less commitment (0.561)

Source: Primary Data (from Questionnaire)

Thus the second factor of stress is renowned as “Extricating Strategy”. Extricating strategy is a method or plan for extricating women from an undesirable situation. It is to leave free or release women employees from a dangerous situation and help them to balance their work and family using strategy.

3. Findings:

The factor examination uncovered that anxiety causing WLB relies on two prevalent components say "Mental Pressure" and "Removing Strategy" of women’s workers in I.T. Divisions. The Psychological weight bothers the women’s workers in their expert life and in addition in their own life. Keeping in mind the end goal to leave the greatest anxiety they embrace the Extricating system of isolating themselves from the anxiety

caused by the works and obligations in their authoritative and individual life. Stress can unfavorably influence on both physical and mental factor of women's. It can likewise bring about sentiments of doubt, dismissal, outrage, and gloom, which thus can prompt medical issues, for example, migraines, stomach disturb, rashes, a sleeping disorder, ulcers, hypertension, coronary illness and stroke. Stress influences the person as well as her condition causing unevenness.

4. Conclusion:

"Work life adjust remains an issue that requires extensive consideration from society. The dynamic condition, where associations regularly work on a 365/day in and day out the calendar and where the innovative advances have made it conceivable." For a representative to be associated constantly, has introduced work life adjust issue into the front line of the brains of numerous. As working women's in the I.T organizations, she needs rich utilizations of learning in her space. This information must be refreshed as per the current improvements to stay with the head in the opposition. Then again, in the Indian setting women's are the ones who need to deal with the youngsters, care for the home front and at the same time dealing with their expert life also. This has caused loads of stress and weight to the women's representatives. Just the individuals who can keep up a harmony between these two can get by in both the organizations. In this atmosphere, overseeing both expert and individual life viable and productively has turned into a noteworthy test for the I.T women representatives.

5. References:

1. Tatheer Yawar Ali, Atif Hassan, Tahira Yawar Ali, and Rizwana Bashir, Stress management in private Banks of Pakistan, *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics And Management Sciences*, 4(3), 2013, 308-320.
2. Nilgun Anafarta, The relationship between work-family conflict and job satisfaction; A structural equation modeling (SEM) Approach, *International Journal of Business and Management*, 6(4), 2011, 168-177.
3. Saira Ashfaq, Zahid Mahmood and Mehboob Ahmad Impact of work-life conflict and work overload on employee performance in Banking sector of Pakistan, *Middle- East Journal of Scientific Research*, 14(5), 2013, 688-695.
4. K.Veerakumar & Dr.S.Shanmugapriya, (2014) article titled "A Study on Work Life Balance among the Dual Working Couples" *Intercontinental Journal of Human Resource Research Review*, Vol-II, Issue-XI, Nov-2014, P.No 14-21.
5. Annie Sam and K. Anitha, Work-Life Balance of Women Academicians – An Empirical Study. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current research*, 2, 2014, 333-335.
6. Jeya Amantha Kumar and Balakrishnan Muniandy, The Influence of Demographic Profiles On Emotional Intelligence: A Study On Polytechnic Lecturers In Malaysia. *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 4(1), 2012, 62-70.
7. S.Pattu Meenakshi and K.Ravichandran, A study on work life balance among teachers working in self-financing engineering institutions, *International Journal of Research in Commerce, IT & Management*, 2(3), 2012, 51-55.
8. Dr.S.Shanmugapriya & G.Gnanaselvi (2014) article titled "Work Life Balance of Male Government Employees in Coimbatore District" *Indo Global Journal of Applied Management Science*, Vol-II, Issue – II, Mar-2014, P.No.164-168.
9. N. Bhuma (2012) *Quality of Work Life of Colleges Teachers*, 1-257 Ph.D Thesis.
10. Malgorzata Kluczyk, The impact of work-life balance on the wellbeing of employees in the private sector in Ireland, *National college of Ireland*, M.B.A Thesis 2013, 1-126.